

USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING AND TEACHING MATHEMATIC USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY LITERACY AND SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on Information Technology (IT) literacy or skills as influencing teachers and students in one of the secondary schools in Terengganu using technology in teaching and learning mathematics. The independent variables to be assessed in this study are information literacy or skills, and the dependent variable is the use of technology in teaching and learning mathematics by using data collection instruments through online questionnaires. The researchers received 40 responses. The quantitative method involved in this study focused on 40 respondents, including 14 teachers and 26 students from One of the secondary schools in Terengganu. The data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The current study used Cronbach's alpha to test the reliability of data results. Hence, Cronbach's Alpha for the independent variable, information technology literacy or skills (0.779), and the dependent variable (0.845). This shows that the results of the data are reliable. The variables, namely the use of technology and learning mathematics, are positively correlated to the use of technology in teaching and learning mathematics.

Keywords: technology, literacy skills, learning, teaching, mathematics

INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are now ubiquitous in the company, home, and workplace, almost permeating every part of our lives. To ensure that schools keep up with societal advancements and make use of the immense potential that ICT offers for teaching and learning, numerous nations have made significant financial investments in ICT integration into the classroom. For instance, Singapore invested S\$2 billion in infrastructure, software, hardware, and teacher training from 1997 to 2002 to facilitate the integration of ICT in schools (Education, 2002). Over the past 20

years, there has been a significant rise in the quantity and variety of technology resources accessible in schools for instructors and students, and the mathematics classroom is no exception. (Gray, Thomas, & Lewis, 2009; Snyder, de Brey, & Dillow, 2016). In their investigation of cultural aspects of mathematics education, Kim and Nguyen (2022) underlined the significance of culturally responsive pedagogy for achieving learning objectives. However, other elements drive teachers and students to use technology during mathematics courses; thus, access to it is insufficient for advancing mathematics teaching and learning. This study aims to investigate how teachers and students at one of the secondary schools in Terengganu are influenced by technology when it comes to teaching and studying mathematics. The following research problems are tackled in this study: Is there a connection between the use of technology in mathematics education and learning and the information literacy and abilities of the teachers and students at one of the secondary schools in Terengganu? Additionally, some researchers have discussed how support from different departments plays a crucial role in school technology integration. According to these researchers, successful school technology integration implementation requires schools to form various school-community partnerships with businesses, other schools, universities, organizations, and people worldwide (Knapp & Glenn, 1996). Several initiatives, such as ICT workshops, are conducted to train teachers and students progressively. The ability to use tools, resources, processes, and systems responsibly to access and evaluate information in any medium and use that information to solve problems, communicate, make informed decisions, and create new products, systems, or knowledge working alone or with others referred to as information technology literacy or skills. The researcher concluded from a prior study that teachers must be proficient in using and managing technological resources in all subject areas to properly incorporate technology into the curriculum (OET, 1995).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Four technology integration predictor variables-principal leadership and support, technology professional development opportunity, teachers' attitudes towards technology in the classroom and the creation of technological partnerships with outside organisations identified by Ritchie and Wiburg (1994) as having an impact on the use of technology in the classroom. Wiburg (1997) postulated the existence of additional significant factors that could impact the extent of technology integration in educational institutions. Technology integration poses a severe challenge to teachers, and students' professional development, particularly regarding information technology literacy. In order to include cutting-edge technology in the classroom, teachers must adopt an integrated approach rather than merely using computers for drills and practice, as stressed by Dias (1999). Because teachers often complain about insufficient time or resources for training, Ritchie and Wiburg (1997) contend that staff development is essential to successfully integrating technology in classrooms. Technology is a vital tool in mathematics instruction for both teachers and students. The researcher concluded from the earlier study that, compared to other advancements, computer use is more difficult to integrate into the classroom. The computer is a significantly more complex system, and in order to explore and learn, it often needs technological assistance (Schrimshaw, 1997). Young teachers who use digital technology in their daily lives can also include it in their teachings, according to Paetsch, Franz and Wolter (2023). The COVID-19 aftermath requires teachers to become internet savvy and use it to help students comprehend subjects, particularly mathematics.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive correlation design is employed in research projects to show the relationship between many variables and give a consistent picture of events (McBurney & White, 2009). In this study, to measure the outcomes, researchers must ask the pre-selected respondents to complete the questionnaire to examine the influence of information technology literacy or skills and internet connections towards the use of technology in teaching and learning mathematics. This research design was adopted to explain the association between the two independent variables: information technology literacy and attitudes towards using technology in mathematics instruction. Salkind (2015) states that a more excellent correlation value denotes a higher degree of relatedness. Thus, the current study investigates the relationship between two independent variables: secondary teachers' and students' information technology literacy or their aptitude for using technology to teach and learn mathematics at Terengganu's secondary school. The numerical index for inferential data analysis statistics, assessed between extremes -1 and +1, will eventually be determined using Pearson Correlation. Information about the relationship between secondary school teachers and students' use of technology in mathematics instructions and learning can be produced using SPSS. Correlation is a statistical technique used to evaluate a potential linear link between two continuous variables, according to Mukaka ((2012). The correlation's strength and magnitude are indicated by the *r*-value, calculated using coefficient statistics. A correlation is a statistic that shows how closely two variables co-vary. According to Webster's Online Dictionary, it can range from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to +1 (perfect positive correlation), with 0 denoting no correlation.

LOCATION OF STUDY

The study was carried out in one of the secondary schools in Terengganu. The research subject and the understanding of secondary teachers' and students' integration of technology in mathematics classes about the variables that have been investigated or determined influence the choice of study area.

POPULATION OF STUDY

The collection of all study participants is referred to as the population. The research's target population is integrating technology in mathematics instruction and learning by teachers and students at one of the secondary schools in Terengganu. All the teachers and students at the school are included in the population for this study.

SAMPLE OF STUDY

A subset of the data chosen from the population is referred to as a sample. Thirty students and ten teachers from the secondary school in Terengganu make up the target sample for this study. As a result, are 40 people in the sample overall, including a teacher and students from Terengganu secondary school.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The stratified sampling approach is the sampling strategy that was applied in this investigation. Stratified samples are chosen by randomly selecting samples from each group after dividing the population into groups, or strata, based on a characteristic. As a result, the population in this study is split into two status-based strata: "teacher and student." Then, out of 20 mathematics teachers, 30 students in the form of four students and 14 teachers were chosen randomly.

DATA COLLECTION

A collection of comprehensive survey forms was modified from an earlier publication, scholarly journal, or other studies conducted by other investigators on related subjects. The questionnaire was created in a digital format using Google Forms, and it was disseminated to the intended respondents via an internet tool—more specifically, the WhatsApp app—to reach them. There were two sections to the questionnaire: part A and part B. The respondent profiles, or as stated in the demographic, comprise Part A. There are ten items in Part B, all of which are questions about independent variables such as IT literacy or skills.

Within three weeks, the 40 respondents' questionnaire responses are gathered from them. A representative from one of the instructors at One of the secondary schools in Terengganu specifically sent the link to the Google Form that contains all of the surveys to the students and teachers at that school. Every respondent has the chance to provide their response to the survey. Respondents can take five to ten minutes to complete the questionnaire.

INSTRUMENT OF STUDY

Regarding the measuring instruments for this quantitative study or research, teachers and students at one secondary school in Terengganu are surveyed using an online form (Google Form) to provide data. The questionnaire has four sections to evaluate the study's hypothesis. The questionnaire has two sections: part A and part B. Respondents must provide essential background information based on demographic questions in section A of the online form (Google Form).

This study used a rating instrument that includes a Likert scale and a categories scale. The question was adapted from Leng (2006) and McCulloch, Hollebrands, Lee, Harrison & Muthu (2018). Because the Likert scale and the scale were thought to be the most effective means of gathering data in which respondents are asked to rate their degree of agreement with a given statement, they were selected. In this study, the Likert scale allows respondents to remain neutral rather than being forced to express an opinion that is either "either or," the categories scale offers a range of options from which they must select. After all responses are received, it is pretty easy to analyze them all.

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

The problem that frequently arises between secondary teachers and students is defined at the study's outset. After identifying every issue, the study's questions, research objectives, and hypotheses are developed. The supervisor had to accept all those components in a single proposal. Subsequently, the data was gathered via the distribution of a series of surveys, comprising ten questionnaires, via an internet platform, the WhatsApp programme. The statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) software is then used to analyse the data collection, and the report's interpretation of the data provides an overview of the study's specifics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Terengganu secondary school is where the responders are from. These respondents must provide some basic information about their personal history. Gender and status are presented as

introductory information. The calculation of mean and standard deviation is explained in this part. The independent variables are information technology literacy or abilities, while the dependent variables are technology usage in math instruction and learning. The questionnaire contains ten items in total that represent the independent variables. After that, it is interpreted into a table explaining every variable.

Table 1. Gender distribution of survey respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent (%)
Male	19	47.5
Female	21	52.5
Total	40	100.0

It is statistically evident that there are more female survey respondents than male respondents, based on the gender distribution of survey respondents shown in Table 1. Of the total respondents, 21 women accounted for approximately 52.5%. Nineteen men, or roughly 47.5% of the total responders, completed the poll out of the remaining.

Table 2. Status distribution of survey respondents

Status	Frequency	Percent (%)
Teacher	14	35
Student	26	65
Total	40	100

It is statistically evident that most survey respondents are students based on the status distribution of survey respondents shown above in Table 2. They represent the most significant percentage (65%) of the 40 total or 26 respondents out of 40. Next in line, or around 35% of the total, are the teachers, or 14 responders.

Mean and Standard Deviation of the use of technology in teaching and learning Mathematics.

Table 3. Mean and Standard deviation of the use of technology in teaching and learning mathematics.

STATEMENTS (ITEMS)	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
Using technology in teaching and learning mathematics benefits students academically.	4.00	0.69
Students are actively engaged in mathematics lessons when technology is used in instruction.	3.73	0.93
Teacher and students are confident in using technology during mathematics lessons.	3.80	0.99
Teachers and students use mathematics software and other educational websites to connect their teaching and learning.	3.70	0.99
Electronic technological resources such as computers, projectors, software, and hardware are readily available in the classroom.	3.23	1.21
Using technology in teaching and learning reduces the amount of time spent on various aspects.	3.85	0.83
Teachers and students are happy using technology in their teaching and learning process.	4.08	0.80
Computer animation is very supportive towards learning because the representation of diagrams is clear and easy to understand compared to the printed photo on paper.	4.30	0.85
Teacher allowed students to use technology for the homework or assignment.	3.60	1.36
The use of technology in classrooms assists teachers and students in doing well during lessons.	4.10	0.98
Average	3.84	0.63

Ten (10) elements from the dependent variable of technology usage in mathematics education are displayed in Table 3 above. The table shows that the average standard deviation is 0.634, and the average mean is 3.84. According to statistical analysis, "Computer animation is very supportive towards learning because of representation of diagrams" has the highest mean, 4.30.

The average rating of 3.84 indicates that most individuals have positive attitudes about using technology in the classroom. It is important to remember that the standard deviations indicate a significant degree of answer diversity, indicating that while opinions are mainly positive, there are discrepancies in a few important areas. Regarding the impact of technology on academic benefits, it seems that respondents (Item 1) have a generally good perspective on the matter, as seen by the high average rating of 4 and the relatively low standard deviation.

Additionally, technology appears to increase student involvement (Item 2), but students' trust in using it (Item 3) is somewhat lower. The higher standard deviations for both items suggest that

respondents' perspectives were not all the same. There is disagreement over whether technology resources should be available in classrooms (Item 5). The low mean rating of 3.23 and the high standard deviation of 1.209 indicate little agreement on this issue. According to most respondents, utilizing technology reduces the time required for various aspects of instruction and learning (Item 6). However, there appears to be some variance in the responses, given the moderate standard deviation.

It seems that instructors and students are generally satisfied with employing technology, based on the high mean value of 4.08 and the relatively low standard deviation (Item 7). Item 8 (the use of computer animation) has a high mean rating of 4.3 and a moderate standard deviation, indicating substantial support. However, teachers still debate whether or not to allow pupils to utilize technology for assignments or homework (Item 9). The low mean rating of 3.6 and the huge standard deviation of 1.355 indicate different points of view. Technology use assists instructors and students in performing well in the classroom, with a mean rating of 4.1 (Item 10). However, the 0.982 standard deviation indicates that there may be some variety in the responses.

In summary, the correlation analysis results show complicated views towards technology in mathematical instruction. Despite generally positive attitudes, there are disparities in how much agreement there is on each aspect of technological integration. It is clear that some topics, like the benefits of technology for learning and happiness, have more consistent support than others, including the availability of resources and the quantity of homework given. On the other hand, opinions on these topics vary widely. Various findings highlight the significance of considering the complexity of various viewpoints when establishing policies and programmes for educational institutions and instructors.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Correlation is a statistical technique used to evaluate a potential linear link between two continuous variables, according to Mukaka (2012). Pearson Relationships The correlation's strength and magnitude are indicated by the r -value, calculated using coefficient statistics. A correlation is a statistic that shows how closely two variables co-vary; according to Webster's Online Dictionary, it can range from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to $+1$ (perfect positive correlation), with 0 denoting no correlation.

Table 4. Correlation Analysis Statistics

Variables	Pearson Correlation (Sig.)	Sig. (2-tailed)	Relationship
Information Technology Literacy or Skills	0.368	0.004	Weak positive relationship

According to Table 4 above, the study's lowest reading is indicated by Pearson's correlation coefficient values for information technology literacy or skills and the use of technology in teaching and learning mathematics, which are $r = 0.368$ and $p = 0.004$ for a two-tailed test with 40 responses. There is a weak positive correlation between technology usage in mathematics education and information technology literacy or abilities.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates how commonplace, as it is in many educational settings across the globe, technological integration is in mathematics instruction at One of Terengganu's secondary schools. The dedication to integrating technology for teaching and learning is evident in the large investments in technical infrastructure and training, including the sizeable sums allotted by Singapore.

The study's overall findings show that both teachers and students are largely in favor of utilizing technology to improve mathematics education. Most of them think that using technology in the classroom increases student accomplishment, fosters engagement, and shortens the time needed for different parts of teaching and learning. Success in integrating technology depends on these favorable mindsets. Demographic data from the poll indicates that female students make up most respondents. The gender distribution here illustrates the diversity of the student body. It is also important to remember that instructors and students participated in the survey, providing a complete picture of technology integration.

The study does, however, also highlight several difficulties with technology integration. The item's low mean rating and wide standard deviation indicate that there appears to be disagreement on the availability of electronic resources in the classroom, such as computers, projectors, and software. This implies that there may be variations in the accessibility and availability of technological instruments. The literature evaluation emphasizes how crucial teacher support and attitudes are to the effectiveness of technology integration. According to the study, teacher confidence and support are two important factors affecting students' performance and involvement with technology integration.

According to the article, for teachers and students to properly incorporate technology, they must get instruction in technology, specifically in information technology literacy and abilities. The results also show how crucial building solid relationships between the community and the school is to facilitate technology integration programs. Additionally, the results of the correlation analysis show a marginally positive association between information technology literacy or skills and the application of technology in mathematics education. This implies that a person's increased information technology literacy and skills and the advancement of technology integration may be correlated, albeit not very strongly. This emphasises how crucial it is to help teachers and students advance their digital literacy.

The research offers significant perspectives on technology integration in mathematics instruction at one of Terengganu's secondary schools. Despite attempts to embrace technology and adopt positive attitudes, problems still need to be fixed, like the lack of financing and the requirement for thorough technical training. The study highlights how crucial teacher support and technological know-how are to the effectiveness of technology integration. In order to ensure that teachers and students can fully utilise technology in the classroom, these insights may be used to build future initiatives to promote technology integration.

This comprehensive evaluation of one secondary school in Terengganu's efforts to integrate technology into mathematics instruction emphasises the necessity of continuing funding for professional development and technology resources to utilise technology's educational potential fully. It also highlights the importance of supporting schools' efforts to integrate technology by promoting digital literacy and fostering a friendly environment. Ultimately, these findings may help

shape future policies and guidelines that support technology integration into mathematical instruction.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author states that no potential conflict of interest exists regarding the findings. This study was conducted with the utmost integrity; it was not influenced or biased by any relationships, employment, grants, stock ownership, patent applications, consultancy work, or jobs. We affirm that no extraneous pressures have compromised the impartiality or trustworthiness of the research's findings and that it has been carried out impartially and objectively.

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